

Astro-neutrino detection at PandaX-4T

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About Yang ZHANG

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SK, BESIII, SNO+, PandaX and JNE

Phys. Rev. D 93, 012004 (2016)
Astropart.Phys. 60 (2015) 41-46

Phys. Rev. D 97, 052011 (2018)
Phys. Rev. D 97, 091102(R), (2018)

NIM.A 1080 (2025) 170755
CPC 48 (2024), 073002
arXiv: 2511.18916 (Accepted by CPL)

BREAKING

Detecting Neutrinos from Nuclear Reactors with Water

Phys.Rev.C 102 (2020), 014002
Phys. Rev. Lett. 130, 091801 (2023)

2010

2016

2018

2022

Now

About particle physics in Shandong U.

>50 faculties in particle physics

Can small detectors be used to detect ν_s ?

Science 2017: ~15 kg CsI(Na)

Coherent elastic neutrino-nucleus scattering

Solar B-8: part of neutrino floor

Miniaturization of the neutrino detectors

PandaX detector

PandaX start

2009

PandaX-I
120kg

2010-2014

PandaX-II
580kg

2015-2019

PandaX-4T
(3.7 tonne)

2020-

As the target mass has reached 4T...

Extraterrestrial
Signal region $< 200 \text{ keV}$

Dark matter

Solar & supernova
Signal region $1 \text{ keV} - 100 \text{ keV}$

Majorana neutrino
Signal region $> 2 \text{ MeV}$

- Solar pp, CPG48 (2024) 091001
- Solar B-8, PRL133 (2024) 191001
- 1) Supernova, CPG48 (2024) 073002;
2) arXiv: 2511.18916 (Accepted by CPL)

Astro- ν detection

Entering into multi-physics phase with one detector.

How to detect

Rn-222/Kr-85 bkg improvement

The bkg also increase proportionally as the target mass...

- ❖ Rn concentration:
 - 5 $\mu\text{Bq/kg}$, 1/6 of PandaX-II
- ❖ Kr concentration:
 - 0.3 ppt natKr, 1/20 of PandaX-II

Kr-85 tagging via
 β - γ coincidence

Search for solar B-8 in PandaX-4T

Exposure: ~0.5 ton*year

NR

Threshold required to be lowered down to 0.3 PE (S1)
Major bkg: Accidentals

ROI (BDT applied)

	ER+NR+AC	8B	Total prediction	Unblind data
S1=2 hit	1.46	1.42	2.88	1
S1=3 hit	0.04	0.29	0.33	0

Indication of Solar B-8 in PandaX-4T

PHYSICAL REVIEW LETTERS 133, 191001 (2024)

Editors' Suggestion

Featured in Physics

Exposure: $\sim 1 \text{ ton} \cdot \text{year}$

Exposure doubled

First Indication of Solar ^8B Neutrinos through Coherent Elastic Neutrino-Nucleus Scattering in PandaX-4T

Introduce the S2-only method
Combine paired and Un-paired

UNIV OF PENN - DEPT OF PHYSICS P.01
 TO: EUGENE BEIER
 SENSATIONAL NEWS! SUPERNOVA WENT OFF
 4-7 DAYS AGO IN LARGE MAGELLANIC CLOUD, 50 KPC
 AWAY. NOW VISIBLE MAGNITUDE 4.5, WILL
 REACH MAXIMUM MAGNITUDE (-1.00) IN A WEEK.
 CAN YOU SEE IT? THIS IS WHAT WE HAVE
 BEEN WAITING 350 YEARS FOR!
 SID BLUDMAN
 (215) 546-3083

Masatoshi Koshiya
Nobel 2002

Start of neutrino astronomy!

A handful of SN neutrino events are recorded...

More SN neutrino data are desirable for the study of SN dynamics & mechanism !
SNEWS: alert astronomical community.

Online trigger

False alarm rate & trigger efficiency

Trigger prob.:

$$p(N_{thr}; T_{SN}; r) = \int_0^{T_{SN}} g(t_s; N_{thr}; r) = 1 - \sum_{n=0}^{N_{thr}-1} \frac{1}{n!} e^{-rT_{SN}} (rT_{SN})^n$$

Bkg rate is checked to be stable (time).

false trigger per week (T_{SN} following T_{SN}):

$$R = \frac{3600 \cdot 24 \cdot 7}{T_{SN}} p(N_{thr}; T_{SN}, r_{bkg})$$

Signal trigger efficiency:

$$\epsilon = p(N_{thr}; T_{SN}, r_{SN})$$

Validation of false trigger rate

Data type	rate	duration	# of observed	# of expected
DD	0.00276/s	85 hours	22	23
AmBe	0.00283/s	153 hours	39	33
BKG runs	0.0004/s	87.5 dasy	11	12

Run0 data

Data type	Rate [/s]	Calendar time	Observed	Expected
DD	2.2×10^{-2}	2.8 days	886	870.6
AmBe	9.7×10^{-3}	3.7 days	288	265
Physical	2.9×10^{-4}	83 days	8	6

Run2 data-2025

❖ **The observed is consistent with the expectation.**

SN burst neutrinos

$$\frac{dN_{\nu A}}{dE_R} = TN_t \int dE_\nu \frac{d\sigma_{\nu A}}{dE_R} \Phi(E_\nu),$$

$$\frac{d\sigma}{dE_R} = \frac{G_F^2 m_N}{4\pi} Q_W^2 \left(1 - \frac{m_N E_R}{2E_\nu^2}\right) F^2(E_R)$$

$[-2.7, 2.4] \text{ ms}$ and $[-0.38, 0.11] \text{ s}$

Signal trigger efficiency

SN model	D=10 kpc	D=168 pc	Duration [s]
$11.2 M_{\odot}$	3.7	1.3×10^4	7.6
$27 M_{\odot}$	8.1	2.9×10^4	8.35

Tier	Required information	Value
Coincidence	initial neutrino time	2025-10-06T14:13:20.333181
Significance	p-values for time bins, width of time bins	[6.11e-06, 1.00], 5.00
Timing	initial neutrino time, neutrino time series	2025-10-06T14:13:20.333181, [0, 1213145668]
Heartbeats	detector status	ON/OFF
Retraction	retract latest	—

Apply to join SNEWS soon.

We can study the solar pp neutrinos.

- ❖ We can dig into low energy region of pp neutrino-e spectrum.
- ✓ Borexino threshold ~ 190 keV.

ROI: [24, 144] keV

$$(8.0 \pm 3.9 (\text{stat}) \pm 10.0 (\text{syst})) \times 10^{10} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2},$$

- ❖ Bkg will be further lowered in the near future.
- ✓ Better precision is expected.

Summary & future prospects

- ❑ PandaX has successfully demonstrated the capability of detecting the astro-neutrino events.
 - ✓ Solar B-8 neutrinos
 - ✓ SN triggers
 - ✓ Solar pp neutrinos
- ❑ PandaX-20T is being proposed and will be constructed in the near future.

King's College London

Thanks for the organization!

BACKUP

Advantages: SN neutrinos at PandaX

Low bkg : extremely low cosmogenics

+

powerful PID

Technical challenges: From keV to (sub)-MeV

We see more light as the particle deposits more energy.

- **PMT desaturation**
- **SS & MS event discrimination**

Fiducialization & bkg estimation